

Alterations in epigenetic systems in A-T neurodegeneration

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Abstract

Ataxia telangiectasia (A-T) is a hereditary multisystemic disease resulting from mutations in the *ATM* gene. Progressive motor function loss as a typical neurological phenotype is resulted from notably degeneration of the Purkinje and granule cells of the cerebellar cortex. However, the molecular mechanism of A-T neurodegeneration is the most poorly understood. Our studies have demonstrated that nuclear accumulation of HDAC4-induced histone deacetylation and EZH-mediated H3K27 tri-methylation contribute to A-T neurodegeneration.

Ataxia-telangiectasia (A-T) is a multisystem disease characterized by neurodegeneration in the central nervous system (CNS)[1-5]. The earliest and most profound neuropathology involves the Purkinje and granule cells of the cerebellum. A-T is caused by mutation of the *ATM* gene, which is ubiquitously expressed throughout development and encodes a serine/threonine protein kinase of the phosphatidylinositol-3 kinase-related kinase (PIKK) family[6]. The best-known function of *ATM* is to ensure the integrity of the genome. After DNA damage, *ATM* activates cell cycle checkpoints, arresting the cycle until DNA repair is complete[7]. Its role in maintaining the health and survival of neurons is complex. Consistent with its function in DNA damage repair[8], *ATM* protects post-mitotic neurons from degeneration by suppressing the cell cycle[9-11]. While non-neurological phenotypes are also found, including immune system defects, germ cell defects, hypersensitivity to ionizing radiation and increased susceptibility to, it is the origins of the CNS motor phenotypes of A-T that are the most poorly understood. *ATM*-deficient neurons are reportedly more sensitive to oxidative damage and show evidence of enhanced DNA damage that increases with age. Yet the pathway that leads from these defects to neuronal cell loss and the other classical neurological phenotypes remains unknown. Epigenetic systems, heritable changes in gene expression that do not involve coding sequence modifications, include DNA methylation, histone modifications and chromatin remodeling, and non-coding RNA (microRNAs) regulation, and have been proposed to be responsible for controlling the expression and function of genes-have emerged as important mediators of development and aging[12-19]. Several diseases are known to have a multifactorial origin, depending not only on genetic but also on environmental factors. They are called "complex disorders" and include cardiovascular

disease, cancer, diabetes, and neuropsychiatric and neurodegenerative diseases[20-26]

In recent years, we have made considerable progress in this area by concentrating our efforts on the epigenetics of the *ATM* genome. We have demonstrated that nuclear accumulation of HDAC4 and EZH-mediated H3K27me3 contribute to A-T neurodegeneration. Strikingly, global histone deacetylation and elevated H3K27me3 were found in not only cerebellum but also several other brain regions such as cortex, brain stem and hippocampus.

Nuclear accumulation of HDAC4 promotes neurodegenerative progression in A-T

We found that *Atm*-deficiency causes nuclear accumulation of histone deacetylase 4 (HDAC4) in neurons and that this shift in HDAC4 location promotes neurodegeneration[27]. Nuclear HDAC4 suppresses MEF2A- and CREB-dependent transcription of neuronal survival genes; blocking HDAC4 nuclear accumulation rescues the degenerative changes found in *Atm*-deficient neurons. Significantly, this rescue activity could be achieved by the overexpression of HDAC4 mutants that were localized to the neuronal cytoplasm, but other HDAC4 mutants, localized to the cell nucleus, not only were incapable of rescuing the *Atm*-deficient phenotype, they actually compromised the phenotype of the wild type. Our findings demonstrate that the A-T phenotype results in part from a loss of cytoplasmic HDAC4 function. To remain cytoplasmic HDAC4 must be phosphorylated and bound to 14-3-3. The HDAC4 phosphatase, PP2A, is down regulated by *ATM*-mediated phosphorylation of its A subunit (PR65). In *ATM* deficiency, enhanced PP2A activity leads to HDAC4 dephosphorylation and nuclear accumulation. We propose that nuclear translocation and cytoplasmic depletion of HDAC4 is a key factor leading to the degeneration of neurons in A-T.

Polycomb epigenetic system is involved in A-T neurodegeneration

As a follow-up to studies on HDAC4, we began to explore the potential involvement of other molecular mechanisms in this process. One part of this work has led to my interest in a second histone modification – histone methylation. I have developed a new set of data showing that polycomb epigenetic system, a chromatin-based repressive mechanism, plays an unexpected role in the process of neurodegeneration in A-T. I found that the activity of EZH2 (*Enhancer of Zeste homolog 2* – the histone methyl-transferase of polycomb repressive complex 2), must be consistently suppressed in neurons in order for them to avoid re-entrance into a cell cycle process and thus begin a pathway that ends in degeneration. I discovered that ATM protein is an essential part of the normal homeostatic process that suppresses EZH2. In both A-T patients and in its mouse models, the physical association of EZH2 with histone H3, specifically lysine 27 – H3K27, is substantially increased. This leads to hypermethylation, creating the trimethyl isoform known as H3K27me3. Normally, ATM-mediated phosphorylation of EZH2 prevents its binding to H3K27 as well as the formation of the PRC2 (polycomb repressive complex 2). When this function fails, the resulting hypermethylation of H3K27me3 causes suppression of multiple brain-specific microRNAs such as miR-124 and -134 as well as cell cycle re-entry. Significantly, knocking down EZH2 in Atm-deficient neurons prevents cell cycle reentry and neuronal death. Our findings reveal that EZH2-mediated formation of H3K27me3 is another key factor in the degeneration of neurons in A T[28].

Future

Our exploration of the roles of these epigenetic systems in A-T neurodegeneration has offered us a clear perspective on the power of these largely unstudied changes to produce far-reaching changes in neuronal function. It is our belief that these changes offer a unique opportunity to advance our understanding of the molecular basis of neurodegeneration. We will begin to explore the ways in which the mechanisms that are at work in the neurodegenerative process in A-T can inform us about the pathogenesis of other seemingly unrelated neurodegenerative diseases.

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